

A Variational Asymptotic Method Based Free Vibration Analysis Of A Thin Pretwisted and Delaminated Anisotropic Strip

S. B. Salunkhe and Prof. P. J. Guruprasad

Department of Aerospace Engineering, IIT Bombay, Powai, Mumbai 400076

ABSTRACT

An asymptotically exact cross-sectional model coupled with geometrically non-linear one-dimensional (1D) theory of modeling delamination in anisotropic strips is proposed. This model is based on the dimensional reduction of laminated shell theory to nonlinear 1D theory using the variational asymptotic method. Delamination is included in the model by following the sublaminar approach. As an application, the ability of the model to capture the trapeze effect, in healthy and delaminated strip, is demonstrated and the results are compared with experimental observations. The stiffness terms obtained from the nonlinear analysis was used in the dynamic analysis. As a first step, only linear stiffness quantities are used within the 1D linear finite element method to investigate the modal behavior of the strip. The utility of the model is demonstrated by determining the natural frequencies and mode shapes for a healthy and delaminated strip.

Keywords: composite beam, delamination, dynamic analysis, finite element method, variational asymptotic method

1 Introduction

Main rotor and tail rotor blades are consistently subjected to high magnitudes of tensile loads. In hinge-less and bearing-less rotor configurations majority of the tensile load is carried by the flexbeams. Flexbeams may be described as pretwisted anisotropic strips that possess varying stiffness parameters along different directions. They undergo elastic bending and twist to accommodate flap, lag and pitch motions. Under such complex deformation modes, the flexbeams, made of laminates, often develop damage in the form of multiple matrix cracking, delamination, among others. Multiple matrix cracking, also known as ‘intralaminar cracking’, is usually the first form of damage observed in experiments on composite laminates. Although it does not cause laminate failure as such, it can cause substantial degradation in the stiffness properties of the component, and also provide pathways for other forms of damage, such as delamination. Delamination between two layers of the laminate, can however be quite detrimental and may directly cause component failure. It is thus very important to develop analysis procedures to account for these damage modes. In particular their effect on the quasi-static deformation characteristic like trapeze effect and modal behaviour is of importance. Only a few studies, have analyzed the effect of delamination on the behavior of the such pretwisted anisotropic strip like configurations. The present effort aims to carefully investigate this problem.

The main objective of this paper is twofold: (i) demonstrate the development of a nonlinear composite strip model in the presence of delamination; and (ii) formulate a dynamic model that accounts for the anisotropic elastic couplings and the damage considered in (i). The development of the nonlinear composite beam model is based on variational asymptotic approach as described in [1] and [2] by simplifying the original 3D problem to a 1D problem. Delamination is included in the model by following the sublaminates approach [3]. The final results for this approach include linear as well as nonlinear stiffness terms that account for the delamination length and location in closed form. Subsequent to the 1D analysis it is possible to completely recover the 3D stress and strain fields along with the in-plane and out-of-plane warping fields. As an application the ability of the model to capture the trapze effect is demonstrated and the results are compared with the experimental observations (see [3]). In this paper, the focus is on the extension of this framework to predict the modal behaviour of pretwisted anisotropic strips in the presence of delamination, model validation and discussion on the model predictability.

2 Beam Kinematics and Formulation

The configuration of the pretwisted anisotropic strip under consideration is shown in Fig. 1; where, l represents the length of the beam, b is the width of the beam, and h is the thickness of the beam, k_1 is the pretwist and the length of the delamination is l_d . The strip has mid-surface symmetric free-edge delamination. Accordingly, the strip is divided into two symmetric sublaminates, groups of plies above and below the delamination interface and a healthy sublaminate in the middle region. The geometry of the strip leads to the following natural small parameters: $\delta_h = \frac{h}{b}$; $\delta_b = \frac{b}{l}$ and $\delta_t = bk_1$ (k_1 is the derivative of the pretwist angle with respect to the length along the strip). The domain of the sublaminates is such that $0 \leq x_1 \leq l$, $-\frac{b}{2} \leq x_2 \leq \frac{b}{2}$ and $-\frac{h}{4} \leq x_3^{(1,2)} \leq \frac{h}{4}$. The development of the kinematics for this problem follows the procedure enumerated in [3]. For brevity, details are omitted and the final expressions for the strains and curvatures obtained are given below.

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{11}^{(1,2)} &\approx \gamma_{11} - x_2 \kappa_3 + k_1 x_2^2 \kappa_1 \pm \frac{h}{4} \kappa_2 + \frac{x_2^2 \kappa_1^2}{2} + \underline{w_3^{(1,2)} \kappa_2} \\ \epsilon_{22}^{(1,2)} &\approx w_{2,2}^{(1,2)} + \frac{h}{4} w_{3,22}^{(1,2)} + \underline{\frac{1}{2} w_{3,2}^{(1,2)^2}} \\ 2 \epsilon_{12}^{(1,2)} &\approx w_{1,2}^{(1,2)} + k_1 \left(x_2 w_{3,2}^{(1,2)} - w_3^{(1,2)} \right) + \underline{\kappa_1 \left(x_2 w_{3,2}^{(1,2)} - w_3^{(1,2)} \right)} \end{aligned}$$

while the curvatures are,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{11}^{(1,2)} &\approx \kappa_2 \\ \rho_{22}^{(1,2)} &\approx -w_{3,22}^{(1,2)} \\ 2 \rho_{12}^{(1,2)} &\approx -2\kappa_1 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In the above 2D strain and curvature expressions, $\{\gamma_{11}, \kappa_1, \kappa_2, \kappa_3\}$ are the 1D strains; w_i 's are the warping terms. The 2D strain terms are used to construct the 2D strain energy density of the strip. VAM calls for the minimization of the strain energy expression with respect to the warping. For a better understanding and visualization of the governing differential equations, it is possible

Figure 1: Strip geometry and co-ordinate system considered in the model. Configuration of the free edge delamination is highlighted and is shown at the structural as well as the cross-sectional level.

to represent them in terms of the generalized forces and moments. This is possible since 2D strains are represented in terms of warpings and consequently 2D strains can be defined in terms of generalized forces and moments. Minimization of the strain energy density also gives rise to a set of natural and essential boundary conditions, apart from the governing equations. These boundary conditions needs to be enforced on the general solution of the warpings. In addition to these boundary conditions, global constraints arising from the definitions of warpings and local rotations, and interface boundary condition, necessary to ensure continuity of warpings across the sublaminates in the healthy region of the strip have to be enforced. After the primary unknowns, the warpings, are determined it is will be possible to determine the strip strain energy, U_{1D} , by integrating 2D strain energy density. The final expression for the strip strain energy density can be written for convenience as below,

$$U_{1D} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_L^T [S_L] \epsilon_L + \epsilon_L^T [S_{LN}] \epsilon_N + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_N^T [S_N] \epsilon_N \quad (2)$$

where the linear and nonlinear 1D strain vectors, ϵ_L and ϵ_N respectively are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_L &= \{\gamma_{11}, \kappa_1, \kappa_2, \kappa_3\}^T \\ \epsilon_N &= \{\kappa_1^2, \kappa_2^2, \kappa_2 \gamma_{11}, \kappa_2 \kappa_3, \kappa_2 \kappa_1\}^T \end{aligned}$$

where the matrices $[S_L]$, $[S_{LN}]$, and $[S_N]$ can be thought of as partitions of a 9×9 matrix $[S]$. The terms of the linear and nonlinear stiffness matrices are presented in [3]. It should be noted that the stiffness terms of a healthy cross-section can be obtained from the terms by putting the length of the delamination $l_d = 0$ i.e by substituting $a = \frac{b}{2}$. Finally, an eigen value problem was setup based on the linear stiffness terms and solved numerically to determine the modal behavior of the healthy and delaminated strip. It should be noted that the formulation, in anyway, is not restricted to linear analysis and can be easily extended to perform a nonlinear dynamic analysis. However, for the purpose of model validation and determining modal frequencies the investigation in this work is restricted to linear analysis. The finite element method (FEM) is used as a numerical tool to model the 1D beam consisting of two node and six degrees of freedom (DOF) elements. The DOF at each node are axial displacement u_1 , transverse displacement u_2 ,

transverse displacement u_3 , slope ϕ and ψ , twist θ . The FE equations of the system are derived by using principle of minimum potential energy for both statics (fully nonlinear) and dynamics (only linear).

3 Results and discussion

Before exploring the utility of the model to predict the modal behavior of the strip in the presence of delamination, numerical calculations were undertaken to validate the framework for a healthy strip configuration. For the purpose of validation, a strip with the geometrical configuration and the material system described in Table 1 was chosen. This system was investigated by Hassan et al. [4] to study the torsional vibration of laminated beams. The influence of fiber orientation on the torsional natural frequency was investigated by modeling laminated beams of different lay-up construction with clamped free boundary condition. Fig.2 shows the variation of the first three natural frequency with change in fiber orientation. It is observed that the torsional frequencies increase with increase in the fiber angle of the laminated beam until it reaches an extremum value, typically in the range between $\theta = 35^\circ - 45^\circ$, then the torsional frequencies decrease gradually with further increase in the fiber angle until it reaches a minimum value at $\theta=90^\circ$. 3D FEM results from Ref. [4] and the current model predictions show good qualitative and quantitative agreement with each other.

Table 1: Material Properties

Materials	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12}/G_{13} (GPa)	ν_{12}
	46.2	14.70	5.35	0.31
Geometry	Length (m)	Width(m)	Height (m)	$\rho(Kg/m^3)$
	0.4	0.04	0.0032	2040

Figure 2: Torsional natural frequencies (Hz) v/s fibre orientation (deg). * represents the Ref.[]

For demonstrating the utility of the model to predict the modal behavior of a delaminated strip, a graphite/epoxy composite material configuration with properties given in the Table 2 was considered. The model was first validated by comparing the static deformation characteristics of a delaminated strip made up of Winckler's type anti-symmetric layup considered in [5] (

Table 2: Material Properties

Materials	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12}/G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}
Graphite /Cyanate	135.6	9.9	4.2	2.5	0.3

Figure 3: Natural frequency ν/s fibre orientation (deg) of anti symmetric layup

$[\alpha_2/(\alpha_2 - 90^\circ)_4/\alpha_2/ - \alpha_2/(90^\circ - \alpha_2)_4/ - \alpha_2]_T$. This layup exhibits strong extensional-twist coupling. In particular, focus was on predicting those nonlinearities that are nonclassical in nature like the trapeze effect. It was observed that zeroth order analysis leads to overprediction of phenomenon like extension-twist coupling in strips, both in the presence and absence of delamination. However, first order analysis leads to accurate prediction of the trapeze effect (see Ref. [3]). VAM based first order analysis, finite-displacement approach based analysis described in [5], and the experimental results are in good agreement. This demonstrates that the complete stiffness (linear and nonlinear) determined by the VAM based technique is asymptotically correct upto the first order. These stiffness terms are used in the dynamic analysis to predict the modal behavior of a delaminated strip.

The influences of fiber orientation and delamination on natural frequency are investigated by modeling laminated beams of clamped free boundary condition. Fig. 3 shows the variation of the different modes of natural frequencies for different ply angle, α . The first and second torsional-extension modes, which oscillate such that the torsion component has the same sign as the extension component is shown in Figs. 3a and 3b. It was observed that the values of these frequencies are identical for $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 90^\circ$. These are two modes are pure torsional in nature. The other component, shown in Fig. 3c, is such that the torsion and extension component have opposite signs and it begins and ends as a pure extension mode. The variation of this mode is exactly opposite to the first two modes of the torsional-extension coupling. Effect of delamination on all the three modes shown in Fig. 3 is apparent. There is significant drop in the natural frequencies of the first two modes of the torsional-extension coupling. The overall frequency drop is more than 40% as the delamination size increases from 0 to 75%. This drop, however, is not as significant in the torsion-extension coupling with opposite sign case.

4 Summary

In this work an attempt was made to analyze the modal behavior of pretwisted anisotropic strips in the presence of delamination. The model development was based on the dimensional reduction of a 3D strip to a 1D problem based on the mathematical framework of VAM. Delamination was accounted for in the model by following the sublaminar approach. Linear and nonlinear stiffness terms for the strip were derived in closed form with delamination size and location as variables. The framework was first validated by comparing the model results to available experimental and other theoretical models in the literature to predict trapeze effect. It was then extended to investigate the effect of delamination on the overall modal behavior of the strip. Model predictions showed good agreement with results available in the literature on the behavior of torsion and torsion-extension coupling modes.

References

- [1] V. L. Berdichevskii. Variational asymptotic method for constructing a shell theory. *Prikladnaya Matematika i Mekhanika*, 43:664–687, 1979.
- [2] D. H. Hodges, D. Harursampath, V. Volovoi, and C. Cesnik. Non-classical effects in non-linear analysis of pretwisted anisotropic strips. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, 34(2):259–277, 1999.
- [3] P. J. Guruprasad, M. Thejasvi, and D. Harursampath. Nonlinear analysis of a thin pretwisted and delaminated anisotropic strip. *Acta Mechanica*, pages 1–18, 2014.
- [4] A. G. Hassan, A. M. Fahmy, and M. I. Goda. The effect of fiber orientation and laminate stacking sequences on the torsional natural frequencies of laminated composite beams. *Journal of Mechanical Design and Vibration*, 1(1):20–26, 2014.
- [5] E. A. Armanios, A. Makeev, and D. Hooke. Finite-displacement analysis of laminated composite strips with extension-twist coupling. *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, 9(3):80–91, 1996.